

Nomenclatural changes for some rice insect pests

T. Barrion, research assistant; and J. A. Litsinger, entomologist, Entomology Department, International Rice Research Institute

Cnaphalocrocis medinalis (Guenee), rice leaf folder

1. Confusion exists among rice entomologists as to the correct spelling of the genus *Cnaphalocrocis* Lederer. In almost all literature pertaining to this pest the genus has been incorrectly spelled *Cnaphalocrosis*; the correct spelling is *Cnaphalocrocis* (Hampson 1896, Fauna of British India, Moths; Vane-Wright 1980, British Museum, personal communication).

2. *Cofana spectra* (Distant), white rice leafhopper

A series of nomenclatural changes has occurred with the white rice leafhopper belonging to the genus *Tettigella*. The species *spectra*, formerly under *Tettigella*, was transferred to *Cicadella* Latreille, because *Tettigella* erected by China and Fennah was a junior objective synonym of *Cicadella* (China and Fennah 1945, Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist. [11]22:711). But in 1966, the International Commission on Zoological Nomenclature suppressed *Cicadella* under the plenary powers citing the Laws of Priority and Homonymy (China and Doyle 1966, Official Index of Rejected and Invalid Generic Names in Zoology, 2nd installment: names 1170-1743, Opinion 647:171). In a recent review of the leafhopper genus *Cofana* Melichar, *Cicadella*, *Tettigella*, and *Tettigoniella* became synonyms of *Cofana* (Young 1979, Proc. Entomol. Soc. Wash. 81[1]: 1-21). Therefore, *Cofana spectra* (Distant) is the correct name.

3. *Cofana yasumatsui* Young, small white rice leafhopper

In the review of *Kolla* Distant (1971, Trans. Shikoku Entomol. Soc. 11[I]:18), Ishihara erected *Yasumatsuus* to accommodate *mimicus* and used *Kollamimica* Distant as the type species. Thus, *Yusumatsuus mimitus* (Distant) became the valid name. But in the recent review of *Cofana* Melichar, *Yusumatsuus Ishihara* became a synonym of *Cofana*. The correct name is *Cofana yasumatsui* Young. To differentiate the common name between the two species of white rice leafhoppers, we propose small white rice leafhopper for *Cofana yasumatsui* (length of male 6.4- 7.5 mm, female 7.2-8.0 mm) and white rice leafhopper for *Cofana spectra* (length of male 8.0-8.6 mm, female 8.5-9.8 mm).

4. *Tryporyza* vs *Scirpophaga*, white and yellow rice stem borers

The use of scientific names for white and yellow rice stem borers has been inconsistent despite several taxonomic studies (I. F. B. Common, 1960, Aust. J. Zool., Melbourne 8[2]:307-347; A. Kapur, 1964, Taxonomy of Rice Stem Borers, p. 3-43, in The Major Insect Pests of the Rice Plant; A. D. Pawar, 1975, The Rice Entomology Newsletter 2:8). Personal communication with Dr. A. Lewvanich (Entomology and Zoology Division, Department of Agriculture, Bangkok, Bangkok 9, Thailand) stressed that the generic characters used by Dr. Common for *Tryporyza* were too narrowly defined to be of generic value. Dr. Lewvanich pointed out that Dr. Common

failed to examine other *Scirpophaga* species occurring outside Australia. Therefore many overlapping characters exist that are impossible to restrict only to *Tryporyza*. We therefore recommend the use of *Scirpophaga innotata* (Walker) for white rice borer and *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Walker) for yellow rice borer.

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